
AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON THE TYPES OF KIDNEY STONES IN CHILDREN OF PUNJAB, PAKISTAN

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this study is to find out the frequency of different types of kidney stones in the children having lower than fifteen years of age.

Methodology: This is an observational research work. The collection of information and samples of stones carried out from one hundred and forty-five patients admitted in different hospitals of Lahore. Dia-Sys analysis kit of urinary calculi was in utilization for the chemical identification of the stone samples. SPSS V. 16 was in use for the analysis of the gathered information.

Results: The average age of the patients was 7.370 ± 4.10 years. The formation of the stones was much common in male gender. The previous history of the family was available in the case of 44.140% children. Most of the (32.40%) kidney stones were available as heterogeneous in their structure. There were complete calcium oxalate kidney stones in only 26.20% structures of stones. Calcium oxalate was also the main ingredient in ninety-eight percent samples of stones, trailed by calcium phosphate in 58.60% samples of stones, ammonium urate presents in 45.50% stone samples & uric acid available in 4.130% patients of this research work.

Conclusion: Most of the kidney stones were available with heterogeneous structure and the main ingredient in their formation was calcium oxalate. The main indication of the formation of the stones is the past history of the family.

KEY WORDS: History, Structure, Kidney, Stone, Phosphate, Heterogeneous, Calcium, Oxalate, Phosphate.

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INTRODUCTION:

The formation of calculi in the urinary tract is a serious issue of health and it is very frequent in some regions of the world. The incidence of this disease varied in accordance with the geographic region, distribution of the ethnic groups and social & economic condition of the people [1]. Localization site of the stone in the urinary system is not consistent in the whole world. The alteration in the localization site is just because of difference in the diet and social & economic condition [1]. The prevalence of this disease in our country is from 10% to 15% [2]. The reason of the formation of stone depends upon the eating habits, abnormalities of anatomic & metabolism [2]. Diet with rich amount of sodium, oxalate, sodium & proteins of animals and low amounts of calcium enhances the risk of the formation of calculi in the urinary tract.

The high amount of the calcium in the diet rummages oxalate available in the gut and reduces the excretion of the urinary oxalate. The management of disease of kidney stones among children requires the workup for metabolism & patients with no history in the family need complete follow ups for the prevention of the recurring of the kidney stones [3]. Hypercalciuria is very frequent complication in the patients suffering from kidney stones of calcium [4]. Dehydration as well as diarrhea can worsen the situation in future [5]. There is very low amount of the information is available on the prevalence of the kidney stones in the children of our country, therefore we conduct this research work to determine the different kinds of the components of the stones in main city of Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY

The duration of this research work was from March 2017 to February 2019. This was an observational

research work. The children of less than fifteen years of age who underwent surgery in different hospitals of Lahore were the part of this research work. The patients available with anatomical anomaly were not the part of this study. We got the ethical approval for the conduct of this study and every patient of his/her parent gave the consent to participate in the work. Every patient filled a questionnaire containing chemical analysis of the samples of stones of every patient carried out. The evaluation of the social and economic condition carried out with the help of the monthly income of the family from all resources. If the income of the family was less than ten thousand took as low social & economic group, ten to thirty thousand income was in medium socioeconomic group & more than thirty thousand was available in high socio-economic group.

Family Information of all the close relative gathered to assess the history of the disease in the family. Washing of the stones carried out & dried at a temperature of thirty-seven centigrade. Dia-Sys analysis kit for urinary calculi was in use for the detection of the composition of the kidney stones. SPSS V. 16 was in use for the analysis of the collected information.

RESULTS

Total 145 children suffering from the stones in urinary tract were the part of this research work. Fifty-nine percent (n: 86) patients were male and 41.0% (n: 59) patients were females. The formation of the stones was very frequent among male. The average age of the patients was 7.370 ± 4.10 years. Majority of the patients was from low socio-economic class with average family income of Rs. 8291 ± 5.28 as available in Table-1.

Table-I: Demographic Characteristics (n=145)

Features	No / Mean	% / SD
Age	7.37	4.10
Mean	8.00	
Children less than 05 years	44.00	30.30
Children between 05-09 years	53.00	36.60
Children more than 10 years of age	48.00	33.10
Males	86.00	59.00
Females	59.00	41.00
Male to female ratio	1.5 : 1	
Monthly family Income (Mean+ SD)	8291.00	5.28
Number of family members(Mean+ SD)	6.20	3.08

Most of the patients 90.0% (n: 130) were utilizing the ground water for needs of drinking. The use of the oxalate excess diets as chocolate, peanuts, raw meat and tomatoes was high as mentioned in Table-2.

Table-II: Source of Drinking Water and Dietary Habits (n=145)

	Parameters	No	Percent
Source of drinking water	Canal	3.00	2.00
	Spring	12.00	8.00
	Ground water	130.00	90.00
	Water intake (Mean, SD) (glasses)	3.04	1.36
	Tea intake /day (Mean, SD) (Cups)	3.00	1.60
Dietary Habits	Cup of milk /day	19.00	13.00
	Eat chocolates frequently	37.00	25.00
	Soft drinks frequently consumed	28.00	19.30
	Frequent Peanuts consumed	40.00	28.00
	Spinach frequent consumption	12.00	8.00
	Chilies frequent consumption	14.00	9.70
	Raw Tomatoes frequently used	54.00	37.00
	Frequent meat intake	22.00	15.00

Medical appearance displayed various symptoms among those patients suffering from the disease of urinary calculi. The main manifestation of pain in abdomen in 70.0% (n: 102) patients, followed by high temperature in 64.80% (n: 94), nausea in 53.10% (n: 77) patients, anuria in 36.0% (n: 53) patients and burning micturition in 45.50% (n: 66) patients.

The presence of the symptoms causes the detection of the problem in most of the patients and 44.14% (n: 64) found with family history in close relatives of formation n of the stones as mentioned in Table-3.

Table-III: Clinical Characteristics

Characteristics		Prevalence	Percentage
Signs & Symptoms	Fever	94.0	64.80
	Abdominal pain	102.0	70.00
	Macroscopic hematuria	40.0	27.60
	Anuria	53.0	36.00
	Burning micturition	66.0	45.50
	Nausea	77.0	53.10
Stone Awareness	Incidental	13.0	8.90
	Symptomatic	106.0	73.00
	Recurrent stone formers	26.0	18.00
Family History	Positive family history	64.0	44.10
	Maternal	21.0	32.80
	Paternal	38.0	59.40
	Both	5.0	7.80

Mix composition of the kidney stone was available in 32.40% (n: 47) patients. We found the stones of pure calcium oxalate in 26.20% (n: 38) samples of stones. The mixture of the calcium oxalate & calcium phosphate was available in 21.40% (n: 31) samples of stone. The percentage of the combination of different compositions is available in Table-4.

Table-IV: Overall Stones Composition (n=145)

Overall Composition	Prevalence	Percentage
Calcium Oxalate	38.0	26.20
Calcium Oxalate + Calcium Phosphate	31.0	21.40
Calcium Oxalate + Calcium Phosphate + Ammonium Urate	47.0	32.40
Calcium Oxalate + Calcium Phosphate + Uric Acid	6.0	4.10
Calcium Oxalate + Ammonium Urate	19.0	13.10
Calcium Oxalate + Struvite + Calcium Phosphate	1.0	0.70
Calcium Oxalate + Struvite	1.0	0.70
Cysteine	1.0	0.70
Xanthene	1.0	0.70

The main ingredient in the composition was calcium oxalate available in 98.0% (n: 143) samples of stones. The composition and their rate in the samples of stones are present in Table-5.

Table-V: Stone Composition Among Patients

Component	Prevalence	Percentage
Ammonium Urate	66.0	45.50
Calcium Oxalate	143.0	98.60
Calcium Phosphate	85.0	58.60
Cysteine	1.0	0.70
Struvite	2.0	1.37
Uric Acid	6.0	4.13
Xanthene	1.0	0.70

DISCUSSION:

The recent data shows distribution of equal same in all the children who are forming stones. The patients with less than fifteen year of age were similar to the patients mentioned in other research works conducted in Armenia [6] & Tunisia [7]. Male dominance was present in this research work which is consistent with many other studies [6, 8-12]. But is more common in stones of gall bladder [12, 13]. It is in favor of the argument that stones of kidney & gall bladder are not two similar clinical entities [14] which is similar to other research works [9, 12, 15]. Pain in abdomen, high temperature, hematuria & anuria were the most frequent symptoms. The past family history has the ability to increase the risk of the formation of the calculi in the urinary tract but it also depends on the eating habits [16]. The past history of family was available in 44.0% patients unlike 12.80% displayed in other research work [14]. Past family history has an association with 40.0% to 50.0% patients of this disease in accordance with many other research works [11, 17, 18].

Most of the children (90.0%) were using ground water to meet their needs of water. There can be the high amount of fluoride in the water which urges the formation of kidney stones [19]. Eating habits and ingredients of diet have an impact on the biochemical features like oxalate, calcium & uric acid [20]. Diet with less amount of calcium can be a factor of risk for the development of kidney stones. Raw meat, tomatoes, peanuts, chocolates & soft drinks are the main reservoirs of oxalate [21] but in our research work, our patients were not taking so much quantity of these foods. The analysis of the urinary calculi is possible with the traditional chemical procedure, Infrared spectroscopy & x-ray crystallography [15, 21,

22]. Unluckily, many research works [14, 23] on the analysis of the kidney stone did not focus on the age of the children in our country except the studies conducted in Karachi [24, 25]. We found the calcium phosphate in 58.60% kidney stones, same result concluded by a research work carried out in South Africa [26]. Among children, most frequent constituent of the kidney stone was the calcium oxalate. The formation was mostly depending upon the socio-economic status of the patients.

CONCLUSIONS:

There were mix components in the kidney stones of children. Adverse social and economic condition, previous history of family for kidney stone diseases and low levels of dietary calcium are the important factor for this issue. The analysis of the kidney stones is very effective for the management of the disease in the very initial stage. There is need of controlled research works to record the part played by the rich diets with calcium & oxalate in the formation of calculi in urinary tract.

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